

The abundance of *Aphis craccivora* Koch. (Homoptera: Aphididae) on 30 groundnut cultivars

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Abstract

Aphis craccivora Koch. is one of the most destructive pests of groundnut, which causes yield losses and transmits rosette virus and catjang disease. The study aimed to observe the seasonal abundance of *Aphis craccivora* Koch. together with the degree of infestation on 30 groundnut cultivars. The correlations between the age of the plant, plant height, pod yield and aphid infestation were also examined. Experiments were carried out at the Genetics and Plant Breeding Field Laboratory, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Mymensingh. Seeds of cultivars were collected from the International Centre for Agricultural Research in the Dry Area (ICRISAT), Hyderabad, India and Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute. The experiment was conducted in a randomized block design with three replications per treatment. Duncan's Multiple Range tests (DMRT) were used to measure specific differences between pairs of means. The results indicated that the abundance of aphids gradually increased from 45 days after planting and reached the peak at 73 days, and then the aphid population gradually declined. Among the cultivars tested, the cultivar DG-2 was found highly susceptible to aphid and ICGV 86635 was less susceptible. The results of the present investigation would be of immense importance in controlling groundnut aphid infestation by using less susceptible groundnut cultivars and adjusting the time of planting.

Keywords: *Aphis craccivora*, abundance, infestation, susceptible, rosette virus, catjang disease, yield

1. Introduction

Groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.) is one of the most important oleaginous crops. It occupies the fourth place in the world among the oilseed crops both in hectareage and production next to soybean, sunflower and cotton (Weiss 1983). Groundnut stands first among the oilseed crops in Bangladesh in terms of yield per hectare and it is fourth in respect of area and production. In Bangladesh, groundnut covers 6.8% of the total area occupied by oilseed crops and 8.69 % of the total production. The average yield of oilseeds is 0.88 t/ha whereas the average yield of groundnut is 1.22 t/acre (BBS 1999). Groundnut is a multipurpose and highly nutritious crop. In Bangladesh, it is used mainly as roasted nuts. Its kernel contains 48% to 50% edible oil as against 30% to 35% in other oilseed crops (Khaleque 1986).

The cultivation of groundnut is hampered due to attacks by several insect pests. Among them, the groundnut aphid (*Aphis craccivora* Koch.) is one of the most destructive pests (Ozigi & Olorunju 1997). It causes 15.87% groundnut yield losses (Jagtap *et al.* 1984). Both nymphs and adults cause damage from seedlings to mature green plants (Imms 1957). The direct and indirect damage is caused by this pest to groundnut through sap removal, irritant and toxic effect, deposition of honeydew, development of sooty mould and transmission of rosette virus (Mayeux 1984). It also transmits catjang disease to groundnut (Raychaudhuri 1981). Damage to groundnut plants results from the sucking of cell sap from plants causing curling of leaves and the appearance of discoloured spots on the foliage. When a large number of aphids are present the plants may gradually wilt, turn yellowish or brown and die (Metcalf & Flint 1951). When aphid infestation is high, yields of groundnuts are markedly reduced (Tarimo & Karel 1987).

Groundnut aphids are well known for their complex life cycles, which involve various combinations of parthenogenesis, sexual generation, wingless and winged forms and alteration of plant host (Romoser 1981). The life history of this insect was studied by Imms (1957). But relatively few studies were carried out on the abundance of this pest, especially in Bangladesh. The present work was, therefore, undertaken to study the abundance of *Aphis craccivora* Koch. on 30 groundnut cultivars. From this view the present experiment was conducted with the following objectives:

- 1) To observe the degree of infestation of *Aphis craccivora* Koch. on 30 groundnut cultivars;
- 2) To study the seasonal abundance of *Aphis craccivora* Koch. on 30 groundnut cultivars;
- 3) To find out the correlations between the age of the plant, plant height, pod yield and aphid infestation

2. Materials and Methods

The experiment was conducted from November to May with 30 groundnut cultivars viz. ICGV 92109, ICGV 92113, ICGV 92116, ICGV 92118, ICGV 92120, ICGV 92121, ICGV 92126, ICGV 93232, ICGV 93233, ICGV 93225, ICGV 93260, ICGV 93261, ICGV 93269, ICGV 93277, ICGV 86635, Dhaka- 1, Cv. 9276, Cv. 4595, Cv. 3203, ICGV 88388, ICGV 86707, M-5, Cv. 65/1484, ACC- 12, ICGS-E-55, DG-2, ICGE-55, ICGV 89259, ICGS-76 and DM-1. Seeds of all ICGVs were collected from the International Centre for Agricultural Research in the Dry Area (ICRISAT), Hyderabad, India, while others were from Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute Centers: *Jamalpur* and *Ishwardi*.

2.1. Study site

The experimental plots were established at the Genetics and Plant Breeding Field Laboratory of Bangladesh Agricultural University (BAU), Mymensingh, which was situated at 24.75° N and a longitude of 90.50 °E. The field was medium-high land under the Brahmaputra alluvial tract having a sandy loam texture and a pH value of 6.5. The previous crop of the experimental field was soybean.

2.2. Weather condition

The climate of the region is characterized by high rainfall and high temperature during the kharif season whilst there is scanty rainfall and low temperature during the rabi season. The weekly meteorological data mainly rainfall, temperature, sunshine and relative humidity (% of RH) were collected from the university weather yard during the study. Weekly rainfall, mean temperature, sunshine and % of RH were calculated from the daily weather chart and have been shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Meteorological data

Month	Week	Air temperature (°C)			Mean relative humidity (%)	Total rainfall (mm)	Sunshine (hrs)
		Max.	Min.	Mean			
January	1 st	23.6	11.7	17.7	81.3	0	5
	2 nd	23.1	8.8	15.9	78.1	0	6.4
	3 rd	26.4	11.2	18.8	75.2	0	7.7
	4 th	24.4	11.6	18	74.2	0	5.8
February	1 st	25.1	12.9	19	73.9	0	5.2
	2 nd	26.9	13.6	20.3	71	0	6.7
	3 rd	29.4	16.6	23	74.6	0.01	6.7
	4 th	27.8	18.5	23.1	79.4	1.6	5.2
March	1 st	28.3	16	22.2	71.4	0.11	6.5
	2 nd	30.8	17.5	24.1	68.7	0	9.1
	3 rd	33	19.2	26.1	65.3	0	9.3
	4 th	32	22	27.1	76.2	1.5	6.8

2.3. Experimental layout

The experiment was conducted in a randomized block design with three replications per treatment (Fig. 1). The unit plot size was 5m x 1.2 m (6m²). The distance between two plots within the block was 0.6 m and between two blocks was 1.2m. The total number of plots was 90 within 3 blocks and 30 plots in each block. The total area is 1228.36m² (57.4m x21.4m).

Figure 1: Layout of the experimental field

2.4.Land preparation

The land was opened with a tractor in the last week of October. Then the land was harrowed, ploughed and cross ploughed several times followed by laddering to obtain a good tilth. After that, the land was levelled and the corners of the plots were spaded and large clods were broken into small pieces. All the weeds and stubbles were removed and the land was finally prepared for planting.

The experimental plot was fertilized with urea, triple super phosphate (TSP), muriate of potash (MP) and gypsum at the rate of 180, 200, 100 and 75kg per hectare respectively. Triple superphosphate, muriate of potash and gypsum were applied at the time of final land preparation while urea was applied three times at intervals. One-third of the dose was applied during land preparation i.e., just before planting, one-third after 30 days of planting and the remaining one-third after 60 days of planting.

2.5.Planting

Seeds of groundnut cultivars were sown during the last week of November at the rate of 100 kg per hectare, maintaining row-to-row and plant-to-plant distances of 30 cm and 20 cm, respectively.

2.6. Cultural practices

Normal cultural practices were followed to keep experimental plots free from weeds. Earthing up, mulching and thinning out were done within 30 days of planting. Crops were exposed to natural infestation and no insecticides were used during data collection.

2.7. Procedure of study

2.7.1. Aphid abundance

Ten plants were randomly selected for each plot and then covered with a thin transparent polythene bag. Then the number of aphids was counted per plant from top to bottom with the help of magnifying glass. Infested and uninfested stems, leaves and flowers were thoroughly checked for correct counting. Counting was done at an interval of 07 days, beginning 45 days after planting. A total of eight samplings were taken before harvesting.

2.7.2. Damage assessment

The extent of damage by groundnut aphids on different cultivars was determined by selecting 20 plants randomly from each row of each plot. Then infested and uninfested plants were counted and expressed in %. Four samplings were taken on 45, 59, 73 and 87 days after planting.

2.7.3. Plant height and yield

Before harvesting, five plants were selected randomly from each of the plots to measure the plant height. The height of the plant was measured by a meter scale. Crops were harvested at the full maturity stage. Groundnut pods were collected separately from each plot and weighed. The yield was expressed in t/ha.

3. Results and discussion

The experimental results of the abundance of aphids on 30 groundnut cultivars and their damage assessment recorded on different days after planting are described below. Plant height and pod yield recorded during harvesting are also reported.

3.1. The abundance of aphids on groundnut plants

The average number of aphids per plant counted from 10 randomly selected plants/unit plots at 45, 52, 59, 66, 73, 80, 80, 87 and 94 days after planting were presented in Table 2 and Fig. 2. The occurrence of aphids at 45 and 94 days of planting was comparatively less than rest of the days of observations. At 45 days, the cultivar ICGV 86635 exhibited a lower number of aphid population (0.96 per plant), which was significantly different from all other cultivars of groundnut. The second lowest number of aphid population (1.81 per plant) was recorded in the cultivar ICGV 86707 that was statistically identical with ICGV 93269, ICGV 88388, ICGV 93261, ICGV 93225, ICGV 92109, ICGV 92116, ICGV 92126, ICGV 93277, M-5, ICGV 93260, ICGV 92118, Cv. 4595, ICGV 92121, Cv. 3203, ICGV 92113, and Cv. 65/1484. The cultivar DG-2 carried the highest

number of aphids (3.29 per plant) on the same days of observations, which was also significantly different from all other cultivars of groundnut, and the nearest was ICGS-76 (2.8 per plant).

Table 2: Abundance of aphids in different groundnut cultivars on different days after planting

Cultivars	Average of aphid/plant at different days								
	45	52	59	66	73	80	87	94	Mean
ICGV 92109	2.07 defg	2.45hijk	2.64hijkl	2.92fghijkl	3.25opq	2.97klm	2.16ghijkl	1.23b	2.46
ICGV 92113	2.29 bcdefg	2.48ghijk	2.65hijkl	2.86ijklm	3.15q	3.06hijk	2.24efghij	1.15bc	2.49
ICGV 92116	2.09 defg	2.52fghij	2.70ghijk	2.89ghijklm	3.18q	2.79n	2.15hijkl	1.17b	2.43
ICGV 92118	2.19 cdefg	2.59efghi	2.80fghi	3.01efghi	3.33mnop	2.86lmn	2.22efghijk	1.13bc	2.52
ICGV 92120	2.02 efg	2.48fghijk	2.58ijklm	2.90ghijklm	3.23pq	2.87lmn	2.30efgh	1.18b	2.45
ICGV 92121	2.27 bcdefg	2.43ijk	2.60ijkl	2.94fghijkl	3.38lmno	3.00kl	2.31efg	1.04bc	2.50
ICGV 92126	2.15 cdefg	2.33jkl	2.51klm	2.87ijklm	3.18pq	2.92klmn	2.14ijkl	1.17b	2.41
ICGV 93232	1.99 efg	2.56fghij	2.68hijk	2.97efghijk	3.43klmn	3.03ijkl	2.36de	1.21b	2.53
ICGV 93233	1.98 efg	2.54fghij	2.70ghijk	3.09def	3.30nopq	2.81mn	2.11jkl	1.20b	2.47
ICGV 93225	1.98 efg	2.5fghijk	2.72ghijk	3.02efghi	3.57ijk	3.06hijk	2.25efghij	1.15bc	2.53
ICGV 93260	2.19 cdefg	2.48fghijk	2.58ijklm	2.76m	3.29nopq	3.01jkl	2.17fghijk	1.58a	2.51
ICGV 93261	1.95 fg	2.18 l	2.38m	2.82klm	3.58hijk	3.20fgh	2.36de	1.25b	2.47
ICGV 93269	1.90 fg	2.28kl	2.85efgh	3.04efgh	3.79defg	3.33efg	2.38de	1.16b	2.59
ICGV 93277	2.15 cdefg	2.55fghij	2.65hijkl	2.84ijklm	3.66ghi	3.31efg	2.35de	1.24b	2.59
ICGV 86635	0.96 h	1.43m	1.59n	1.78n	2.07r	1.61o	0.97m	0.93c	1.42
Dhaka-1	2.64 bc	2.7def	2.77fghij	2.99efghij	3.81def	3.19ghi	2.23efghijk	1.21b	2.69
Cv. 9276	2.40 bcdef	2.68defg	2.90efg	3.11de	3.73efgh	3.12hij	2.07kl	1.23b	2.66
Cv. 4595	2.22 cdefg	2.5fghij	2.63hijkl	2.94fghijkl	3.46ijklm	3.04hijk	2.11jkl	1.24b	2.52
Cv. 3203	2.27 bcdefg	2.47ghijk	2.70ghijk	3.04efgh	3.87de	3.36ef	2.29efghi	1.17b	2.65
ICGV 88388	1.92 fg	2.34jkl	2.52klm	2.79lm	3.50jkl	2.98jkl	2.13jkl	1.08bc	2.41
ICGV 86707	1.81 g	2.44ijk	2.46lm	2.88hijklm	3.58hijk	3.00jkl	2.03 l	1.17b	2.42
M-5	2.17 cdefg	2.62efghi	2.71ghijk	3.03efgh	3.69fghi	2.96ijklm	2.02 l	1.23b	2.55
Cv. 65/1484	2.31 bcdefg	2.54fghij	2.62ijkl	2.99efghij	3.60hij	3.07hijk	2.17fghijkl	1.24b	2.57
ACC-12	2.79 b	3.01bc	3.19bc	3.47c	4.20c	3.41de	2.47d	1.24b	2.97
ICGS-E-55	2.42 bcdef	2.84cd	3.01cde	3.22d	3.92d	3.53cd	2.33def	1.17b	2.81
DG-2	3.29 a	4.00a	4.25a	4.56a	5.41a	4.85a	3.88a	1.29b	3.94
ICGE-55	2.53 bcde	2.67defgh	2.84efgh	3.06efg	4.13c	3.58bc	2.71c	1.23b	2.84
ICGV 89259	2.59 bcd	2.77de	2.97def	3.21d	4.18c	3.63bc	2.80bc	1.21b	2.92
ICGS-76	2.80b	3.01bc	3.16bcd	3.47c	4.38b	3.68bc	2.90b	1.24b	3.08
DM-1	2.78b	3.11b	3.33b	3.69b	4.44b	3.71b	2.71c	1.17b	3.12

Figures followed by the same letter(s) in a given column do not differ significantly, as per Duncan's Multiple Range Test

At 52 days after planting the number of aphids increased. The highest number of aphids per plant was found in DG-2 (4 per plant), which was significantly different from all other cultivars. The second lowest number of aphid populations (3.11 per plant) was recorded in the cultivar DM-1, which was statistically identical to ACC-12 and ICGS-76. The lowest number of aphid populations (1.43 per plant) was found in ICGV 86635, which was also significantly different from all other cultivars. The second lowest number of aphids (2.18 per plant) was estimated in ICGV 93261, which was statistically identical with ICGV 93269 and ICGV 92126.

Figure 2: Line graph of the abundance of aphids in different groundnut cultivars

At 59 days and 66 days after planting the number of aphids increased more the previous, significantly highest was in the DG-2 (4.25 and 4.56 per plant) and significantly lowest was in the ICGV 86635 (1.59 and 1.78 per plant).

Observations 73 days after planting the highest number of aphid populations was observed in each variety. This was the peak of the number of aphids on groundnut plants, and then the number of aphids declined. On 73 days, the highest number of aphids was found in the DG-2 (5.41 per plant), which was significantly different from all other cultivars. The second highest number of aphids was recorded in the DM-1, which was also significantly different from all other cultivars except ICGS-76. The lowest number of aphid populations was found in the ICGV 86635 (2.07 per plant), which was significantly different from all other cultivars. The second lowest number of aphids was estimated in the ICGV 92113 (3.15 per plant), which was statistically identical with ICGV 92116, ICGV 92126, ICGV 92120, ICGV 92109, ICGV 93260 and ICGV 93233.

At 80 days and 87 days after planting the number of aphids per plant decreased gradually. At the days of 80, the significantly highest number of aphids was found on the DG-2 (4.85 per plant) and after seven days (87 days after planting) the number decreased (3.88 per plant). The significantly lowest number of aphids per plant at 80 days after planting was found on the ICGV 86635 (1.61 per plant). At 87 days after planting, the highest abundance of aphids per plant was found in the DG-2 (3.88 per plant) and the lowest was found in the ICGV 86635 (0.97 per plant).

At 94 days after planting, the vigour of groundnut plants decreased and aphid populations also decreased. At this point of observation, the aphid populations were statistically identical in all the cultivars except ICGV 93260 and ICGV 86635. The highest number of aphids per plant was recorded at 1.58 in the ICGV 93260 and the lowest recorded in the ICGV 86635 (0.93 per plant).

Considering the mean population over the entire observation period, it was found that the highest number of aphid population was in the cultivar DG-2 (3.94 per plant) and the lowest was in the cultivar ICGV 86635 (1.42 per plant).

The results indicated that the abundance of groundnut aphids gradually increased from 45 days of planting and reached a peak on 73 days and then gradually declined. The highest aphid abundance was observed on 73 days of planting in all the groundnut cultivars. Aphids suck the cell sap from vegetative parts of the plant within 73 days of planting. Plants attained full vegetative stage, which might be responsible for the highest abundance of aphids. The physiological stage of the groundnut plant, at this stage, might also be more favourable to aphid attack. Premchand *et al.* (1989) reported that the peak of aphid abundance occurred from January to February. Charoenridhi *et al.* (1979) reported that peak numbers of *Aphis craccivora* occurred between December and March. Kumar *et al.* (1997) reported that the aphid population reached its peak during February. Akhilesh *et al.* (1997) reported that the *Aphis craccivora* population declined during March. In the present study, groundnut was planted on 26 November 2000 and the plant stage was 73 days on 7th February. Therefore, the findings of the present study are in agreement with the findings of Kumar *et al.* (1997) and Premchand *et al.* (1989). Faleiro *et al.* (1990) reported that the abundance of *Aphis craccivora* was negatively correlated with maximum daily temperature, and sunshine and positively correlated with minimum daily temperature, RH and rainfall. According to Prasad *et al.*

(1984), a maximum ambient temperature of around 20°C and fairly high relative humidity favour the population build-up of *Aphis craccivora*. Akhilesh *et al.* (1996) reported that an average atmospheric temperature of 19.4°C along with a relative humidity of 76.2% was favourable for the population build-up of *Aphis craccivora*. In the present study, the average temperature and relative humidity of the 1st week of February 2001 were 19°C and 73.9%, respectively.

3.2. Extent to plant damage by aphids

The percentages of infested plants recorded at 45, 59, 73 and 87 days after planting were presented in Table 3 and Fig. 3.

Table 3: Mean per cent of aphid-infested plants of different groundnut cultivars on different days after planting

Cultivars	Percent infested plant at different days				Mean
	45	59	73	87	
ICGV 92109	12.72ghi	15.88ghij	18.84ijk	13.26hijkl	15.18
ICGV 92113	13.83efgh	16.35fgh	18.28jk	13.95fghi	15.60
ICGV 92116	12.53ghi	16.37fgh	18.22k	13.35hijk	15.12
ICGV 92118	12.74ghi	16.51fg	18.97ijk	13.58ghij	15.45
ICGV 92120	12.16hi	15.45hijk	18.25k	14.13efgh	15.00
ICGV 92121	13.68fgh	15.43hijk	19.20ij	14.08efgh	15.60
ICGV 92126	12.97ghi	15.29ijk	18.73jk	13.20hijkl	15.05
ICGV 93232	12.27hi	16.49fg	19.66hi	14.57def	15.75
ICGV 93233	12.27hi	16.77fg	19.13ijk	13.04ijkl	15.30
ICGV 93225	12.09hi	16.36fgh	20.63fg	13.63fghij	15.68
ICGV 93260	13.27gh	15.82ghijk	18.75ijk	13.39hijk	15.31
ICGV 93261	14.47gh	14.86k	20.66fg	14.56def	15.89
ICGV 93269	12.02hi	17.19ef	21.94de	14.59def	16.44
ICGV 93277	13.04gh	16.60fg	21.24 ef	15.00de	16.47
ICGV 86635	6.76j	9.78 l	11.80 l	5.96m	8.58
Dhaka-1	15.65bcde	16.52fg	21.92de	13.76fghij	16.96
Cv. 9276	14.38defg	17.16ef	21.34ef	12.80jkl	16.42
Cv. 4595	13.56fgh	16.10ghi	20.17gh	13.03ijkl	15.72
Cv. 3203	13.89efgh	16.61fg	22.30d	14.11efgh	16.73
ICGV 88388	12.09hi	15.45hijk	20.18gh	13.00ijkl	15.18
ICGV 86707	11.01i	15.03jk	20.71fg	12.50kl	14.81
M-5	13.41gh	15.57fg	21.28ef	12.38 l	15.91
Cv. 65/1484	13.67fgh	16.07ghi	20.87fg	12.47ghijk	16.02
ACC- 12	16.20bcd	18.90bc	23.71c	15.29d	18.53
ICGS-E-55	14.55cdefg	17.84de	22.29d	14.38defg	17.27
DG-2	21.97a	26.47a	31.38a	23.95a	25.94
ICGE-55	15.48bcdef	17.13ef	23.53c	16.68c	18.21
ICGV 89259	15.90bcd	18.24cd	24.24bc	17.17bc	18.89
ICGS-76	16.49b	18.53cd	24.90b	17.88b	15.45
DM-1	16.45bc	19.66b	25.05b	16.60c	19.44

Figures followed by the same letter(s) in a given column do not differ significantly, as per Duncan's Multiple Range Test

At 45 days after planting the cultivar ICGV 86635 recorded the lowest percentage (6.76%) of infestation and was statistically different from all other cultivars. The highest infestation (21.97%) was observed in the DG-2, which was also statistically different from all other cultivars.

The percentages of aphid-infested plants increased at 59 days after planting in comparison to 45 days. Again, the cultivar ICGV 86635 recorded the lowest aphid infestation (9.78%), which was statistically different from all other cultivars. Significantly highest infested plants were recorded in the DG-2 (26.47%), which was also significantly different from all other cultivars.

Figure 3: Line graph of per cent of aphid-infested plants of different groundnut cultivars

The aphid infestation percentage remarkably increased at 73 days of planting in comparison to 45, 59 and 87 days. The cultivar ICGV 86635 recorded significantly the lowest aphid infestation (11.80%) and the cultivar DG-2 showed significantly the highest aphid infestation (31.38%).

The percentage of aphid infestation decreased at 87 days after planting in comparison to 73 days. The cultivar ICGV 86635 showed the lowest infestation (5.96%) rate, which was the statistically highest percentage of infestation (23.95%), which was also statistically different from all other cultivars.

Considering the mean plant infested over the entire growing period, it was found that the highest aphid infestation was observed in the cultivar DG-2 and the lowest in the cultivar ICGV 86635.

Bottenberg & Subrahmanyana (1997) reported that aphid infestation ranged from 6 to 32% in groundnut plants. Considering the plant infested over the entire growing period it was found that aphid infestation ranged from 5.96 to 31.38% in groundnut plants. So, the findings of the present study are in agreement with the findings of Bottenberg & Subrahmanyana (1997). Damage by aphids declined from 80 days of planting in almost all the groundnut cultivars. At this time groundnut plants almost passed their vigour phase and the plant became more mature. The plant tissues were no more succulent and not favourable for aphid attacks. Alegbejo *et al.* (1999) reported that a significant negative correlation was observed between the age of plants and the number of *Aphis craccivora*.

3.3. Plant height

The height of different cultivars was recorded before harvesting (182 days after planting). The mean height ranged from 89.53 cm to 10.06 cm. The cultivar ICGV 86635 was found to be the tallest (89.53 cm) followed by ICGV 92118. The cultivar DM-1 was found to be the shortest (10.06 cm), which was statistically different from all other cultivars (Table 4 and Fig. 4).

Table 4: Plant height of different groundnut cultivars before harvesting

Cultivars	Plant height (cm)			
	Plot 1	Plot 2	Plot 3	Mean
ICGV 92109	52.90	53.00	46.70	50.87defgh
ICGV 92113	50.00	45.50	41.30	45.60defgh
ICGV 92116	54.10	53.50	54.50	54.03cdefg
ICGV 92118	58.90	87.00	72.70	86.20a
ICGV 92120	79.80	58.20	53.10	63.70bc
ICGV 92121	52.50	48.90	54.50	51.97cdefg
ICGV 92126	72.70	64.00	52.60	63.10bc
ICGV 93232	71.00	56.90	75.70	67.87b
ICGV 93233	68.80	69.10	71.60	69.83b
ICGV 93225	48.50	45.20	49.40	47.70defgh
ICGV 93260	63.40	57.40	47.70	56.17cde
ICGV 93261	53.50	59.40	56.40	56.43cd
ICGV 93269	52.00	54.70	53.30	53.33cdefg
ICGV 93277	59.10	56.00	50.10	55.07cdef
ICGV 86635	97.70	77.10	93.80	89.53a
Dhaka-1	56.10	59.20	49.00	54.77cdefg
Cv. 9276	53.30	48.05	50.67	50.67defgh
Cv. 4595	52.75	47.90	50.50	50.38defgh
Cv. 3203	45.20	45.90	46.50	45.87defgh
ICGV 88388	46.70	77.70	45.50	56.63cd
ICGV 86707	44.30	44.00	45.30	44.53defgh
M-5	45.40	46.00	45.50	45.63defgh
Cv. 65/1484	45.00	44.80	45.90	45.23defgh
ACC-12	46.40	47.10	45.50	46.33defgh
ICGS-E-55	39.90	38.00	39.20	39.03h
DG-2	46.60	47.10	46.00	46.57defgh
ICGE-55	52.50	43.40	43.00	42.97fgh
ICGV 89259	44.10	43.80	44.00	43.97efgh
ICGS-76	42.80	42.50	82.80	42.70gh
DM-1	10.10	10.00	10.07	10.06i

Figures followed by the same letter(s) in a given column do not differ significantly, as per Duncan's Multiple Range Test

Plant height did not correlate with aphid infestation. Among the 30 cultivars, ICGV 86635 was the tallest cultivar and was found less susceptible, while DG-2 though moderately tall was found highly susceptible. The genetic makeup of the cultivar might be responsible for the different reactions of different groundnut cultivars to aphids.

Figure 4: Line graph of plant height of different groundnut cultivars

3.4. Pod yield

The groundnut pod yield (mt/ha) was presented in Table 5 and Fig. 5. Significantly lowest yield was recorded in the DM-1 (0.56 mt/ha), which was statistically different from all other cultivars. The second lowest yield (1.83 mt/ha) was found in the Cv. 4595, which was identical to ICGS-76. The significantly highest yield was recorded in the ICGV 93261(4.55 mt/ha), which was statistically different from all cultivars. The second highest yield (4.03 mt/ha) was found in the ICGV 93277, which was also statistically different from all other cultivars.

Table 5: Yield performance of different groundnut cultivars

Cultivars	Pod yield (mt/ha)			
	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	Mean
ICGV 92109	2.67	3.00	3.00	2.89ghi
ICGV 92113	3.08	3.08	3.08	3.08fg
ICGV 92116	2.67	2.67	2.58	2.64jk
ICGV 92118	3.17	3.17	3.25	3.20ef
ICGV 92120	3.17	3.37	3.33	3.29de
ICGV 92121	3.42	3.42	3.33	3.39de
ICGV 92126	2.33	2.33	2.33	2.33lm
ICGV 93232	2.92	2.83	2.92	2.89ghi
ICGV 93233	3.33	3.42	3.50	3.42d
ICGV 93225	4.17	3.83	3.50	3.83c
ICGV 93260	2.83	3.00	3.17	3.00gh
ICGV 93261	4.58	4.58	4.50	4.55a
ICGV 93269	3.67	3.83	3.83	3.78c
ICGV 93277	4.08	4.00	4.00	4.03b
ICGV 86635	2.08	2.00	2.08	2.05o
Dhaka-1	2.33	2.33	2.42	2.36lm
Cv. 9276	2.83	2.83	2.75	2.80hij
Cv. 4595	1.75	1.83	1.92	1.83p
Cv. 3203	2.92	2.83	2.92	2.89ghi
ICGV 88388	3.08	2.67	3.00	2.92ghi
ICGV 86707	3.53	3.33	3.33	3.40de
M-5	2.16	2.33	2.25	2.25mn
Cv. 65/1484	3.50	3.33	3.25	3.36de
ACC-12	2.83	2.67	2.67	2.72ij
ICGS-E-55	2.42	2.50	2.56	2.47kl
DG-2	2.00	2.08	2.08	2.05no
ICGE-55	2.33	2.50	2.33	2.39lm
ICGV 89259	2.75	2.75	2.75	2.75ij
ICGS-76	2.16	1.83	2.00	2.00op
DM-1	0.67	0.50	0.50	0.56q

Figures followed by the same letter(s) in a given column do not differ significantly, as per Duncan's Multiple Range Test

Pod yield did not correlate with aphid infestation. Among the 30 cultivars the lowest yield was found in the DM-1 and the highest was in the ICGV 93261, while ICGV 86635 was found less susceptible and DG-2 was highly susceptible. The genetic make-up of the cultivar might be responsible for the different reactions of different cultivars to aphids.

Figure 5: Line graph of yield performance of different groundnut cultivars

4. Conclusions

Different groundnut cultivars showed different reactions to the groundnut aphid. It was found that ICGV 86635 was less infested and DG-2 was highly infested. The groundnut aphid infestations in different cultivars were found in the following order of intensity: DG-2 > DM-1 > ICGS-76 > ACC-12 > ICGV 89259 > ICGE-55 > ICGS-E-55 > Dhaka-1 > Cv. 9276=Cv. 3203 > ICGV

93269=ICGV 93277 > Cv. 65/1484 > ICGV 93232 >M-5 > ICGV 93225 > ICGV 92118 > Cv. 4595 > ICGV 93260 > ICGV 92121 > ICGV 92113 > ICGV 93233=ICGV 93261 > ICGV 92109 >ICGV 92120 > ICGV 92116 > ICGV 86707 > ICGV 88388 > ICGV 92126 > ICGV 86635.

The full vegetative stage of the plant, minimum daily temperature, RH and rainfall favoured the population build-up of *Aphis craccivora* Koch. Pod yield and plant height did not correlate with aphid infestation.

The results of the present investigation would be of immense importance in controlling groundnut aphid infestation by using less susceptible groundnut cultivars and adjusting the time of planting. The use of any resistant cultivars of any crop has several advantages as the resistance is inherent in the plant itself with no extra costs involved in the control measures. Moreover, it does not deteriorate the quality of the environment and is generally compatible with other methods of pest control.

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